

D6.2

Practice abstracts batch 1

Document ID	D6.2 Practice abstracts batch 1
Due date	30.04.2024
Delivery date	19.04.2024
Dissemination level	PU - Public
Document version	Final (FV)

This project is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101083961. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Funded by
the European Union

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Acronym	LIKE-A-PRO
Title	From niche to mainstream - alternative proteins for everybody and everywhere
Grant Agreement Number	101083961
Call	HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01
Project coordinator	ASOCIACION PARA LA INVESTIGACION DESARROLLO E INNOVACION DEL SECTOR AGROALIMENTARIO - AIDISA (CTIC-CITA)
Work Package	WP6
Lead Beneficiary	Food & Bio Cluster Denmark (FOODCLUSTER)

AUTHOR(S) AND CONTRIBUTORS	
Name:	Organisation:
Britt Sandvad	Food & Bio Cluster Denmark (FOODCLUSTER)
Thomas van der Lee	Foodvalley NL
Aleksandra Luszczynska, Ewa Kuliś-Stefańczyk	SWPS University
Floor Severens	Stichting Nationale Week Zonder Vlees
Ainhoa Bilbao	GAIKER

PEER REVIEWS		
	Date:	Name:
Review 1	11.04.2024	Francisco de Araújo Vasquez (SAFE)
Review 2	17.04.2024	Meneviş Uzbay Pirili (ZEYTINCE)
Approval coordinator	19.04.2024	Morena Silvestrini (CTIC-CITA)

DOCUMENT HISTORY			
Version:	Date:	Modifications:	Author:
0.1	22.03.2024	First draft	Britt Sandvad
0.2	26.03.2024	Final draft ready for peer reviews	Britt Sandvad, Thomas van der Lee, Aleksandra Luszczynska, Ewa Kuliś-Stefańczyk, Floor Severens, Ainhoa Bilbao
0.3	18.04.2024	Reviewer's suggestions included	Britt Sandvad, Francisco de Araújo Vasquez, Meneviş Uzbay Pirili
0.4	18.04.2024	Final comments and revisions	Morena Silvestrini
Final (FV)	19.04.2024	Final version	Britt Sandvad

Table of contents

Executive summary.....	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Methodology	5
3. Practice Abstracts	7
4. Conclusions.....	12

List of figures

Figure 1. Slide from WP6 November meeting explaining the Practice Abstract concept.....	6
Figure 2. Slide from WP6 November meeting showing example of a Practice Abstract.	6
Figure 3. Timeline for development of Practice Abstracts.	7

Executive summary

The LIKE-A-PRO project aims to facilitate sustainable and healthy diets by shifting promising alternative proteins and products from niche to mainstream. To make a protein dietary shift possible, the food industry must focus on diversifying the alternative protein sources and developing new appealing products. The LIKE-A-PRO project aims to support this work by empowering food system actors with practical knowledge.

Following the project's objective of disseminating the resulting innovative knowledge at European level, a number of summaries for practitioners in the EIP-AGRI common format (Practice Abstracts; PAs) will be delivered. A total target number of 10 PAs is foreseen for the project, divided into 2 batches of 5 each. This is the first batch expanded into 7 PAs to clarify the message and keep it within the character limits we decided to split one of the subjects selected into four abstracts.

Considering the common EIP-AGRI format provided on the EIP-AGRI website, a template was created by FOODCLUSTER to collect PAs from LIKE-A-PRO partners.

A section dedicated to LIKE-A-PRO PAs will be created on the EIP AGRI /EU CAP Network website also including general information on the project and links to audio-visual material and project website.

1. Introduction

The current deliverable titled “D6.2 Practice Abstracts batch 1” presents the objectives, methodology and results of the collection of the first batch of Practice Abstracts (PAs) describing different successful activities organised and delivered in the LIKE-A-PRO project aiming to support the protein shift. The objective is sharing project outputs so other actors can use them and see the added value and benefits for end-users who will implement that activity presented in the PAs.

The second batch of PAs will be developed by the end of the project.

This deliverable is divided into 4 parts:

Chapter 1 – Introduction: the structure of the deliverable.

Chapter 2 – Methodology: describes the process of collecting and reporting the PAs.

Chapter 3 – Practice Abstracts: 7 PAs described in English.

Chapter 4 – Conclusions: concludes the report and provides information on the use of the outcomes and the next steps.

2. Methodology

In the Grant Agreement (GA) it is described that end-user material will be produced in the form of summaries for practitioners in the EIP common format. Since the application has been submitted, the EIP-AGRI Network has become part of EU CAP Network and the EIP-AGRI website will no longer be updated after April 2023, and it refers to the EU CAP Network website. This website informs you that the EIP-AGRI common format for Horizon multi-actor projects 2021-2027 is under development and will soon be published. An email contact to EU CAP Network support facility confirms that the new common format will be similar to the existing one, and the character limit for the summary should not be hugely changed. Based on this, we decided to produce the PAs batch 1 in the old/existing format in order to deliver it in due course. If the new template for EU CAP NETWORK is developed in due time for the second batch this will be implemented at this stage. Otherwise, the same template will be used for the second-round collection.

To meet the objective of the task, a protocol was identified to develop the template for the LIKE-A-PRO practice abstracts and to collect the first batch of PAs.

At the bi-monthly WP6 partner meeting in November 2023, the concept of PAs was explained to the participants using definitions and examples derived from the EIP-AGRI common format (see figures below).

What is a Practice Abstract?

EIP-AGRI common format

- EIP-AGRI → EU CAP Network
- The EIP-AGRI common format for Horizon multi-actor projects 2021-2027 will soon be published (says so on the website – and has for a long time 😊).

A short summary that describes a main information/recommendation/practice that can be used by the end-users in their daily practice.

- Main results/outcomes of the activity (expected or final)
- The main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?
- Links to audio-visual material (photos, films, etc.) are included as much as possible.
- 2000 characters

This project has received funding from the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101083961. Funded by the European Union

Figure 1. Slide from WP6 November meeting explaining the Practice Abstract concept.

Practice abstracts – format and content

KPI = 10 (5 M18 + 5 M48)

Practice Abstracts could be derived from each of these topics (examples):

- Understanding the key determinants of consumers' choices of alternative protein food products (T1.1)
- Including food system actors in system mapping (T1.3)
- Using X method to obtain Y result (WP1, 2, 3)
- Sustainable protein sources for novel food ingredients (optimisation of extraction, purification, and fractionation processes)
- Product development – how to collaborate on improving taste and texture (WP2)
- Campaign roll-out (WP6)
- True price method for social and environmental costs calculation
- Regulatory aspects for Novel Food

Practice summary

Practice abstract 1

Short title (in English):
Communication: Building bridges and Bringing Together Stakeholders

Short summary for practitioners (in English):
In the first press release about agroBRIDGES, two objectives were addressed: 1) stakeholder involvement from the beginning of the project and 2) awareness of the potential to improve local producers' market position and reduce intermediaries' margin from SFSCs. The press release was based on the press release from the agroBRIDGES project management, but adjusted to be more relevant for the Danish target groups and a Danish context in general. The press release was sent out to a handpicked media group within the agrifood sector. Addressing this purpose in a precise and relevant way meant that the press release resulted in many articles in highly relevant professional journals / magazines such as:
*PolicyWatch
*FødevarerWatch
*AgriNews
*Elevktiv Landbrug
*Fødevarer Fokus
*Food Supply DK
*Landbrug-Aktuel
Which in turn resulted in direct contact with farmers, producers and other stakeholders within the Stakeholder Groups relevant for agroBRIDGES:
*Producers and farmers
*Distributors
*Consumers
*Academics and researchers
*Policy makers and public food procurers
*Technology networks, hubs and clusters
*Civil society

A clear description of "what's in it for the farmers / producers" did allow the stakeholders to assess the relevance for themselves immediately. Which is thought to be the reason why so many have responded promptly to confirm their interest. Thereby, it has been possible to select actors, who adequately reflect the ecosystem in the region, which form the basis of the MAP (Multi-Actor Platform).

This project has received funding from the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101083961. Funded by the European Union

Figure 2. Slide from WP6 November meeting showing example of a Practice Abstract.

At this meeting, we also agreed on a timeline for choosing and writing the PAs (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Timeline for development of Practice Abstracts.

Based on input from the partners and the coordinator, we decided on these subjects:

1. Alternative Proteins and Novel Foods: EU Food Regulation and Safety Issues
2. Novel Food: Curse or blessing?
3. What motivates consumers to choose plant-based alternative protein food products?
4. How to motivate consumers to choose plant-based alternative protein food products?
5. Can we motivate consumers to choose insect-based alternative protein food products?
6. How to motivate consumers to choose insect-based alternative protein food products?
7. Famous Dutch sustainable behavioral change campaign 'Week Without Meat' now also successfully launched in Belgium.

PA #3/4 and #5/6 was originally written together, but to clarify the message and keep it within the character limits we decided to split them up which also explains that **we end up with seven PAs instead of the required five.**

Using the EIP-AGRI common format template, the WP6 leader developed an Excel template for the partners to fill in with their PAs.

3. Practice Abstracts

In this chapter, the 7 PAs are displayed in English. Some of the PAs are also available in local language. All PAs will be displayed on the EU CAP Network website together with general information on the project and links to audio-visual material and project website.

Title	Alternative Proteins and Novel Foods: EU Food Regulation and Safety Issues
Authors	Ainhoa Bilbao // GAIKER
Short summary for practitioners	<p>Consumers are evolving towards healthier and more sustainable eating habits and are looking for environmentally friendly food options. Therefore, alternative proteins, such as those derived from sources other than conventional animal sources, i.e. plant, microbial, oceanic, fungal and insect sources, are of great interest and have undeniably captured their attention.</p> <p>The food industry has taken note of this growing trend and is moving to meet the demand through the development and production of alternative proteins. However, the development of alternative proteins poses challenges for food industry operators.</p> <p>How are alternative proteins regulated in Europe?</p> <p>Although not all alternative proteins are considered novel, those that do not have a history of consumption to a significant degree before 15 May 1997 will be treated as novel foods requiring pre-market authorisation under Regulation (EU) 2015/2283. Therefore, it is essential to conduct safety assessments of the protein to cover potential food safety risks, including toxicity, allergenicity, safety of its production method and dietary exposure arising from consumption. Furthermore, it is important to note that alternative proteins used as feed are not subject to the EU's novel food regulation, as they are instead regulated according to European feed rules (while food and feed obtained via genetic engineering techniques are themselves regulated differently). However, due to consumer demand for information on the use of non-GMO feed, some producers have adopted specific private standards to ensure transparency. It is possible that similar requests by consumers could be made for alternative proteins used in feed in the future.</p> <p>Safety issues of alternative protein sources</p> <p>Each protein source has its own advantages and in some cases limitations in terms of nutritional and safety aspects, thus a case-by-case approach is required to provide with sufficient data to oversee that technological progress in this area is balanced with robust safety standards. Food safety must therefore be a primary requisite when companies develop alternative proteins and food products, whether novel or not. Quality and safety assessment, including toxicological, nutritional and allergenicity analyses, are integral parts of the LIKE A PRO in vitro tests to be carried out on the obtained alternative protein extracts and the final products formulated in the project.</p> <p>The expected outcomes will contribute to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provide useful scientific data and information about change in nutritional value (essential amino acid profile and branched-chain amino acids- BCAAs) or nutritional disadvantages (antinutritional factors: protease inhibitors and polyphenols) • verify, on the basis of the scientific evidence available, that final products formulated with alternative proteins do not pose a risk to human health (by genotoxicity and allergenicity in vitro assays) • enable food businesses to easily categorize their alternative proteins products and follow the legal requirements in terms of safety attributes.

Title	Novel Food: Curse or blessing?
Authors	Thomas van der Lee // Foodvalley NL
Short summary for practitioners	<p>In 2023, Partners from The Protein Community gathered to deliberate on the challenges and opportunities surrounding novel food products and regulations. The significance of novel ingredients in propelling innovation and sustainability within the protein sector was underscored. However, the discussion highlighted the intricate nature of navigating complex regulations, ensuring food safety, gaining market acceptance, and effectively scaling products employing novel food ingredients and processes.</p> <p>Key takeaways from the session included:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Participants voiced frustration over the extensive timelines associated with EFSA Novel Food Regulations. While certain regions like Singapore and the US exhibit relatively shorter approval periods, the EU's process can stretch from 30 to 60 months. Shortening authorization timelines must however not compromise food safety. 2: Safeguarding intellectual property (IP) before embarking on the regulatory process was emphasized. Failure to do so could potentially lead to public disclosure, jeopardizing businesses' proprietary information. 3: Suggestions were made to explore alternative routes, such as preparing a document demonstrating why an ingredient does not qualify as a novel food or seeking partnerships with other firms or academic institutions to streamline the process. 4: Enlisting the services of advisors to assist in navigating the complexities of assessing a product's eligibility as a novel food was strongly recommended. 5: The importance of considering market dynamics from the outset was highlighted. Understanding customer needs, crafting compelling commercial narratives, and focusing on becoming experts in specific categories were deemed crucial for success.

Title	What motivates consumers to choose plant-based alternative protein food products?
Authors	Aleksandra Luszczynska, Ewa Kuliś-Stefańczyk // SWPS University
Short summary for practitioners	<p>Are you looking to promote alternative protein products made with algae, seaweed, pulses, and other plants? Our systematic review of research on the role of psychosocial factors can help to design effective advertising campaigns, education programs, and promotions. By identifying the factors consistently linked to consumers' choices, you can better understand why people buy, try, and are willing to eat alternative protein products.</p> <p>Across studies, the top psychosocial factors systematically related to consumers' choices of plant-based alternative proteins include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • knowing how to cook/prepare a meal with alternative proteins, • familiarity (past experiences with this type of food), • believing that a switch from traditional proteins to alternative proteins would be good for the environment, • believing that it is a healthy choice to replace traditional proteins with alternative proteins, • animal welfare/empathy towards animals., • younger age and higher education. <p>When promoting the consumption of plant-based alternative food, consider featuring young people cooking a meal or presenting a recipe incorporating an alternative protein product. Highlight the three major benefits: it's healthy (good) for you, good for the</p>

	planet, and shows respect for animal welfare. This message is particularly effective for younger, better-educated men and women.
--	--

Title	How to motivate consumers to choose plant-based alternative protein food products?
Authors	Aleksandra Luszczynska, Ewa Kuliś-Stefańczyk // SWPS University
Short summary for practitioners	<p>To truly motivate potential consumers towards adopting a plant-based (including pulses, seaweed, etc.) or algae-based alternative protein diet, campaigns, consultations, or other actions should incorporate the following strategies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing knowledge on how to cook/prepare a meal with alternative proteins, • Communicating the benefits of switching from traditional proteins to alternative proteins would be good for the environment, • Communicating the health benefits of replacing traditional proteins with alternative proteins, • Communicating benefits for animal welfare. <p>Younger consumers and people with higher education tend to be more open to trying and incorporating this food into their daily diet. Campaigns/actions focusing on young people are more likely to succeed.</p> <p>For example, the campaign motto could be “Make choices that are good for you, animals, and the planet. Learn how to prepare your meal with plant-based alternative proteins.”</p>

Title	Can we motivate consumers to choose insect-based alternative protein food products?
Authors	Aleksandra Luszczynska, Ewa Kuliś-Stefańczyk // SWPS University
Short summary for practitioners	<p>We conducted a systematic review of research, testing the role of psychological and social factors that explain why people buy, try, and are willing to eat alternative protein products made of/with insects. Knowing which factors consistently influence consumer choices may help to design effective promotion campaigns, education programs, and advertising strategies to encourage more people to embrace these alternative protein options.</p> <p>The top psychological and social factors consistently related to consumers’ choices of insect-based alternative proteins include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • feeling adventurous, excitement and curiosity while trying insect-based food, • liking new foods, • communication with important others (e.g., such as athletes and successful young entrepreneurs) who themselves eat this type of food and are encouraged to try it, • trust in technology used in alternative protein production, • perceiving health benefits and/or low health risks related to trying insect-based proteins. <p>Consumers are more likely to be men and younger people.</p> <p>The evidence suggests that promoting the consumption of insect-based alternative food is more effective when role models who approve of/encourage to try insect-based protein products are included. Another option is to highlight that alternative protein production cares to account for advanced technology that proposes a safe, healthy, and modern product. Promotion campaigns may also emphasize the excitement of trying novel foods and stress the approval of important others (e.g., models young men admire), increasing consumers’ motivation.</p>

Title	How to motivate consumers to choose insect-based alternative protein food products?
Authors	Aleksandra Luszczynska, Ewa Kuliś-Stefańczyk // SWPS University
Short summary for practitioners	<p>To increase the motivation of potential consumers, campaigns, consultations, or other actions that aim to promote insect-based alternative protein intake should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate that trying insect-based food is an exciting adventure (Dare to try!); • Prompt curiosity (Aren't you curious?); • Present photos, videos, and comments of role models attractive to young men, encouraging them to try or include insect-based protein food in their diets. Ideally, the role models should be from the same country as the potential consumers; • Communicating the trustworthiness of novel technology used in alternative protein production; • Communicating healthiness and/or low health risks related to eating food with insect-based proteins; • Prompt knowledge about how this type of food is produced and why it is healthy. <p>As male consumers and younger, educated people are more likely to try or include this type of food in their regular diet, the most successful campaigns/actions are those that target young men.</p> <p>For example, the campaign motto could be “He dares to try it. Do you care to dare? Learn more about new food with insect-based proteins.”</p>

Title	Famous Dutch sustainable behavioural change campaign 'Week Without Meat' now also successfully launched in Belgium
Authors	Floor Severens // Stichting Nationale Week Zonder Vlees
Short summary for practitioners	<p>The 'Week Without Meat' is an annually recurring behavioural change campaign that aims to make the general population aware of the positive impact of eating less animal foods on the climate crisis. By challenging people to not eat meat for a week, and inspiring them instead with easy and delicious plant-based recipes, the campaign wants to make people experience how easy and delicious it actually is to eat plant-based more often. This behavioural change campaign first started in The Netherlands in 2018 and is rolled out by non-profit foundation Week Without Meat. The campaign has proven its success in the Netherlands with over 60% of the population that knows the campaign and about 1 in 5 adults that participate each year. As part of the LIKE-A-PRO project, the campaign is set to be introduced into 5 other European countries being Belgium (2023), Denmark (2024), Germany (2024), Austria (2025) and Spain (2025). The first Week Without Meat was introduced in Belgium between 23-29 October 2023. The communication mix consisted of, amongst others:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A strong PR (free publicity) strategy • Out of home exposure (e.g. digital banners in public transport stations) • Social media campaigning • A campaigning website • A reverse graffiti campaign in order to spread awareness about the Week Without Meat close to supermarkets • A collaboration with 24 high end restaurants • Local ambassadors in each Belgian province • A free vegan winter BBQ in one of the biggest Belgian cities <p>By using this mix of effective communication strategies, the campaign achieved great results: 27% of Belgian adults were aware of the campaign, 3% of the adult population participated (some 313,000 people) and 97% of participants plans to keep eating less or no meat in the future. This way, the first edition of this campaign has already managed to inspire long term sustainable behavioural change amongst the Belgian population and even more impactful results are expected during the following upcoming editions.</p>

4. Conclusions

The LIKE-A-PRO project has in this first batch developed 7 PAs, following the common EIP-AGRI format in order to meet the project's objective of sharing good practices with practitioners and to help boost the protein change in Europe.

The PAs illustrate replicable experiences that can be used as models for similar purposes and enable others to exploit project results. This includes the following insights:

- Food safety must be a primary requisite when companies develop alternative proteins and food products, whether novel or not.
- The intricate nature of navigating complex regulations, ensuring food safety, gaining market acceptance, and effectively scaling products employing novel food ingredients and processes is highlighted.
- In terms of motivating consumers to choose alternative protein you need to distinguish between plant-based and insect-based products.
- When promoting the consumption of plant-based alternative food, consider featuring young people cooking a meal or presenting a recipe incorporating an alternative protein product.
- As male consumers and younger, educated people are more likely to try or include insect-based protein in their regular diet, the most successful campaigns/actions are those that target young men.
- By using a mix of effective communication strategies, a behavioural change campaign can achieve great results.

The PAs have been sent to the EU CAP Network on April 19th 2024, and will be displayed on their website.

Next step will be to develop an additional batch of PAs by the end of the project.